

HEALTH CARE EXPENDITURE AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE AND LIFE EXPECTANCY : A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN INDIA & USA

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1

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: Present study aims to make a comparative study between the health care expenditure spent by India and USA Governments and its impact of GDP and the Expectancy of life in both the countries.

Design/Methodology: The data collected from the datasets of world bank from the year 2010 to 2019 for the variables used to analyse the study.

Findings: The results suggest a strong correlation between healthcare spending and economic income indicators. t-Test revealed a sizable disparity between the healthcare spending made by the Indian and USA Governments.

Practical Implications: The significant observations on the impact of GDP on the health spending of India and USA are analysed.

Originality/value: This study shows the implications of the policy including the fact that a healthy population positively affects the nation's economy as a whole.

Keywords: Healthcare Expenditure, Life Expectancy, Health Outcomes

Paper Type: Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

"Real riches is not in money and silver coins, but in one's health." —**Mohandas K. Gandhi**

For any nation to experience the required economic growth and development, enhanced human capital is seen to be crucial (Novignon et. Al. 2012; Romer D 1996).

The expansion of human capital in terms of health and education has a long-term beneficial impact on per capita income, according to the neoclassical growth model (Romer D 1996). Healthier individuals contribute at the work place, when compared to others, they are more

productive, earn better incomes, and are likely to save and invest more with the hope of living longer. Therefore, efforts to promote health should always be a country's primary development objective because it is a crucial component of sustainable development (Health systems WHO, 2000). Any country should prioritise investing in the health care industry. Evidence suggests that the economy gains greatly from investments in health. An instance is a WHO report (WHO Commission on Macroeconomics and Health & World Health Organization, **2001**) indicated that the economic growth rate increased by 0.35% annually for every 10% rise in life expectancy at birth. Similar to this, poor health is viewed as a significant financial burden and is primarily responsible for 50% of the growth gap between advanced and developing economies.

For more than couple of decades, researchers been investigating to examine the relationship between healthcare spending and health sector outcomes in light of the significance of public health and its contribution to the economy. Spending on healthcare can lead to improved health opportunities, which can build human capital , boost productivity, also improves the performance of an economy. As a result, wise investment in many facets of Healthcare would decrease poverty while also raising GDP, productivity, and income.

Total health expenditure (THE) has gradually grown into a significant concern. In developing countries' unequal growth in the global economy is due to more than just the rising Total health expenditure. If greater life expectancy is thought of as a leverage for a person's investment in health services, it may be anticipated that as life expectancy rises, the propensity of health care investment will likewise rise.

Depending on their level of economic development, countries have different per capita health expenses. Low-income nations only spend up to \$30 per person on healthcare, compared to high-income nations, who spend \$3,000 per citizen on average. It's crucial to take into account healthcare spending as a proportion of GDP (Oni LB . 2014). While some nations spend more than 12% of their GDP on healthcare, others only spend up to 3%. (Erdil and Yetkiner 2009).

Healthcare spending and its effects on economic growth are significant economic drivers. Some studies have shown a favourable inverse association between GDP growth and improvements in health (Bloom et. Al 2004; Bloom & Canning 2003; Öztürk & Topcu 2014). The burden on families and the progress of nations alike can be reduced by establishing a reliable healthcare system. In fact, OCED Observer reports that a simple 10% increase in life expectancy translates in economic growth of roughly 0.4% annually, demonstrating the importance of a robust healthcare system for a thriving economy.

The healthcare industry is a barometer for the value of human capital. The rising healthcare expenditures improve the productivity of human capital, which in turn promotes economic expansion (Kurt S 2015; Piabuo & Tieguhong 2017). However, There is lively discussion on which healthcare investments are most beneficial for GDP expansion and how

much should be spent on each (Agenor, 2008; Boucekkine et. Al 2008; World Health Organisation, 2003).

In the proposed study, the relationship between public health spending and economic growth in India and the US, as well as life expectancy, is investigated. The positive impacts of health investment on a country's economic development have been verified by several researchers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Contradictory conclusions might be drawn from previous empirical research of the connection between healthcare spending and sector outcomes. For example, Public health care spending has been shown to have a favourable effect on health sector performance in studies of 30 OECD nations, Sri Lanka, Russia, and Nigeria (Rana et al. 2018; Anand & Ravallion 1993; Patricio et al. 2008; Imoughele & Ismaila 2013).

Healthcare spending, along with other variables, was found to have a significant effect on health outcomes by Akinkugbe and Mohanoe (2009). Public health expenditure was found to have a considerable and stronger effect on the health status of the poor in a cross-country data analysis conducted by Gupta et al. (2001).

In addition, the infant and child mortality rate is found to have an inverse relationship to the amount of money invested in public health, as was found by Barenberg et al. (2017), Maruthappu et al. (2015), and Kumar et, al. (2013) for India, 176 countries, and India, respectively. These studies were conducted on India.

Recent research by Arthur and Oaikhenan (2017) utilising World Bank data in 40 SSA countries found that health spending has an inelastic but significant effect on health outcomes. Based on their research, they concluded that increased healthcare spending significantly decreased mortality rates and marginally increased life expectancy.

A 10% increase in public health spending decreased the death rate by roughly 2% across all age groups in India, as shown by the research of Farahani et al. (2010).

Universal health coverage, of which health expenditure is a significant component, was found to have a beneficial effect on life expectancy in 193 countries by Ranabhat et al. (2018).

On the other hand, Heuvel and Olaroiu (2017) found no correlation between health care spending and life expectancy across 31 European countries.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are presented below:

1. To examine the Healthcare spending, GDP, and Life expectancy, particularly with relation to two countries: India (Developing nation) and USA (Developed nation).
2. To make a comparative study between the Health care expenditure spent by India & USA Governments .
3. To research how the GDP and health spending affect the life expectancy in India and the USA.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology includes Data Collection, Variable selection and Selection of tools for data analysis.

Data Collection: Data was retrospectively collected from the datasets of world banks . Total expenditure on health, GDP and Life Expectancy were gathered for the year 2010 to 2019 from various databases. Since the secondary data is taken from the world bank, it should be taken as trustworthy and authentic. (Table 1& 2).

Variables: Variables include Health care expenditure & GDP which are Independent variables and dependent variables include Life Expectancy.

Statistical Tools : Means for the three variables i.e., Health Care Expenditure, GDP, Life Expectancy were calculated .

T-test was done to make a comparative study between the health care expenditure spent by India & USA Governments .

Multiple Regression was done to study the effects of GDP & healthcare spending on life expectancy in both India & the US.

ANALYSIS

The objectives of the study were taken in to account for the statistical analysis.

Objective 1: To examine healthcare spending, Gross Domestic Product, and life expectancy, particularly in comparison to India and the USA.

Table 1: Total expenditure on health, GDP and Life Expectancy (USA)

Date	USA Health Exp	USA Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)	USA GDP(Billions of US \$)
31-12-2010	16.2592	78.49	15048.96444
31-12-2011	16.1985	78.64	15599.72812
31-12-2012	16.1754	78.79	16253.97223
31-12-2013	16.0645	78.94	16843.19099
31-12-2014	16.2533	78.914	17550.68017
31-12-2015	16.5241	78.888	18206.02074

31-12-2016	16.8443	78.862	18695.11084
31-12-2017	16.8058	78.836	19479.62006
31-12-2018	16.6871	78.81	20527.15603
31-12-2019	16.7671	78.87	21372.57244
Mean	16.45793	78.804	17957.70161

Source 1: <https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>

Source 2: <https://www.cms.gov/Research-Statistics-Data-and-Systems/Statistics-Trends-and-Reports/NationalHealthExpendData>

Table 2: Total expenditure on health, GDP and Life Expectancy (INDIA)

Date	INDIA Health Exp	INDIA Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)	INDIA GDP(Billions of US \$)
31-12-2010	3.2721	66.426	1675.615
31-12-2011	3.2463	66.874	1823.05
31-12-2012	3.3294	67.322	1827.638
31-12-2013	3.7494	67.77	1856.722
31-12-2014	3.6196	68.07	2039.127
31-12-2015	3.5957	68.37	2103.588
31-12-2016	3.5043	68.67	2294.798
31-12-2017	2.936	68.97	2651.473
31-12-2018	2.9518	69.27	2702.93
31-12-2019	3.0141	69.5	2831.552
Mean	3.356067	67.97133333	2108.326778

Source 1: <https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>

Source 2: <https://www.cms.gov/Research-Statistics-Data-and-Systems/Statistics-Trends-and-Reports/NationalHealthExpendData>

From the table 1 & 2, it is evident that:

- The Mean value of USA health Expenditure is **16.457** whereas that of India is **3.356**.
- US Government spends **16.457 %** of GDP on healthcare whereas Indian Government spends **3.356 %** of GDP on healthcare.
- The Mean value of USA GDP is **17957.70161** (Billions of US \$) whereas that of India is **108.326778**(Billions of US \$)
- The Mean value of USA Life Expectancy is **78.804** years whereas that of India is **67.971** years

Objective 2: To make a comparative study between the Health Care Expenditure spent by Indian & USA Governments .

T-test was used to determine the disparities between Indian and American government spendings on health care.

Ho: No significant difference is found between the Health Care Expenditure spent by USA & Indian Government

H1: There exists a significant difference between the Health Care Expenditure spent by USA & Indian Government.

Table3a: T-test to Ascertain the Differences in Health Care Expenditure of USA & INDIA

Group Stat				
Health Exp	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std Error Mean
USA	10	16.457930	0.2992695	0.946373
INDIA	10	3.321870	0.2922144	0.0924063

Table 3b: Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	df.	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
HEA EXP	Equal variances assumed	0.276	0.606	99.313	18	<..001	13.1360600	.1322692	12.8581727	13.4139473
	Equal variances not assumed			99.313	17.990	<.001	13.1360600	.1322692	12.8581614	13.4139586

From the above table 3a & table 3b, it can be inferred that the t-value was found to be significant at 0.01 level. Hence, there is a significant difference between the Health Care Expenditure of USA & INDIA. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

USA government spends much more on Health expenditure compared to Indian government. This is evident from the above mean value.

Objective 3a: To examine how the India's GDP and health spending affect the expectancy of life

Ho: A Significant impact of GDP , Health Expenditure was not found on Life Expectancy in India

H1: A significant impact of GDP , Health Expenditure was found on Life Expectancy in India

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.990 ^a	0.979	0.974	0.167080

a.Predictors : Constant), INDIAHEP, INDGDP

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.303	2	4.651	166.623	<.001 ^b
	Residual	0.195	7	0.028		
	Total	9.498	9			

a. Dependent Variable: India Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)
b. Predictors: (Constant), INDIA HEP, INDGDP

The results of ANOVA show that the model is significant for this data.

Model		Un Standardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Const)	62.772	0.855		73.427	<.001
	INDGDP	0.156	0.009	0.922	16.926	<.001
	IINDIAHEP	-0.998	0.191	-0.284	-5.212	.001

a. Dependent Variable: INDIA Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)

Life Expectancy= 62.772+0.156 (INDGDP)- 0.998 (INDIAHEP)

Thus, from the results of the above table 4a, 4b and 4c, it is observed that impact of GDP and the Health Expenditure on Life Expectancy in India is significant.

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Objective 3b: To study the impact of GDP and Health Expenditure on Life Expectancy in USA.

Ho: There is no significant impact of GDP ,health expenditure on life expectancy in USA

H1:There is a significant impact of GDP , health expenditure on life expectancy in USA

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.687 ^a	0.473	0.322	0.113871

a. (Predictors : Constant), USAHEP, USAGDP

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.081	2	.041	3.137	.106 ^b
	Residual	0.091	7	0.013		
	Total	.172	9			

a. Dependent Variable: USA Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)
b. Predictors: (Constant), USA HEP, USAGDP

The results of ANOVA show that the model is insignificant for this data.

Table 5c:Coefficients^a

Model		Un Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	82.702	3.252		25.430	<.001
	USA GDP	7.513E-5	0.000	1.138	2.331	.049
	USA HEP	-.319	0.226	-.690	-1.413	.201

a. Dependent Variable: USA Life Expectancy from Birth(Years)

Life expectancy =82.702+ 0.00075(USA GDP)-0.319(USA HEP)

Thus, from the results of the above table 5a, 5b & 5c, it is observed that impact of GDP is significant as $P < 0.05$ and Health Expenditure on Life Expectancy in USA is insignificant as $P > 0.05$.

LIMITATIONS

Although there weren't any time series data for recent years at the time of study, the data was only accessible for 10 fiscal years, from 2010 to 2020, giving researchers the rare chance to investigate the factors that influence health care spending in India and the USA.

Two variables, namely GDP and life expectancy, were the only ones used in this analysis. Finally, several methodological problems that were still present could open up new possibilities for panel data for future analysis.

CONCLUSION

The current study not only examines the relationship between India and the United States' total health care spending, GDP, and life expectancy, but also illustrates the statistical association between these three variables. It was discovered that the GDP and health expenditure had a considerable impact on the life expectancy in Indians and the USA residents.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The findings indicate that overall health care spending is more responsive to GDP than life expectancy in a nation. The typical relationship between health spending and GDP can be established by undertaking more longitudinal data analysis for many emerging nations.

Further analysis can also be done by adding few more variables such as Labour Productivity, Mortality rates, Per-Capita Income etc. & its influence on Health Care Expenditure.

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